

Research

Screening of Different Rice Genotypes for Blast Disease Resistance in Gokarna-Lalitpur, Nepal

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Abstract: Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is the major cereal crop of Nepal belonging to the Gramineae family. Every year, its production is highly affected by devastating rice blast disease caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cavara. With the view to recognize the resistant genotypes against both leaf and neck blast disease, a rice blast screening nursery trial was conducted in Gokarna, Lalitpur in 2021 and 2022, consisting of 163 genotypes in 2021 and 181 genotypes in 2022, including two susceptible checks, Taichung-176 and Manjushree-2. Rice genotypes were screened for resistance following the rice standard evaluation system (SES) scale (1). Disease scoring was performed qualitatively at two stages: first at tillering for leaf blast and second at maturity for neck blast. 163 genotypes were scored in 2021 and 181 genotypes were screened in 2022. Among them, 114 genotypes were tested in both years, while 49 and 64 genotypes were unique to the years 2021 and 2022 respectively. Altogether, 227 genotypes were screened for blast resistance in two years. Results showed that out of 114 recurring genotypes, only 16 genotypes for neck blast and 35 genotypes for leaf blast showed the same resistance level in both years. The information revealed from this study could be helpful for rice blast disease management and utilizing these resistant and moderately resistant genotypes for further resistance breeding programs.

Keywords: Rice blast, Resistant, Genotypes, Screening, Susceptible

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Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa*) is a cereal crop belonging to the Gramineae family and is native to Asia. It serves as the staple food for over half of the world's population. Rice accounts for approximately 21% of the total energy consumed per person worldwide and contributes about 15% of the protein intake per person (2). Rice blast, caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*, is widely recognized as one of the top ten plant diseases caused by fungi due to its economic damage to rice production (3). Rice blast disease poses a significant challenge for rice cultivation on a global scale. It is a widespread problem that

affects rice crops wherever they are cultivated, and frequent outbreaks of the disease are a recurring issue (4). The disease can affect all aerial parts of the plant, with most infections occurring on the leaves, characterized by diamond-shaped lesions with a grey or white center (5). Leaf blast affects panicle quantity and individual grain weight by stunting plant height (6). Stem node infections lead to the development of barren panicles, while late neck infections result in "broken necks," chalky kernels, and sterile grains (7). Yield losses due to rice blast can reach as high as 70-80% under predisposing factors such as high mean temperature values, relative humidity above 85-89%, presence of dew, drought stress, and excessive nitrogen fertilization (8). Neck blast disease causes more significant reductions in both yield and quality compared to leaf blast, as demonstrated by (9). While there is typically a strong positive correlation between resistance to leaf and neck blast, there have also been instances where resistance to leaf blast does not necessarily indicate resistance to neck blast (10).

In Nepal, rice is the most important crop, followed by maize and wheat, covering an area of 1.47 million hectares with a total production of 5.6 million tons and a productivity of 3.80 t/ha (11). Approximately 20% of the National AGDP and 7% of the National GDP of Nepal is accounted for by rice, which also satisfies over 50% of the grain demand and more than 30% of the calorie needs of the Nepalese population (12).

The first documented occurrence of blast disease in rice in Nepal can be traced back to 1964 when it was recorded in Thimi, Bhaktapur (13). The rice blast, a global impediment to rice production, also affects Nepal without exception. Rice blast is prevalent throughout the rice-growing areas of Nepal, from the Terai Plain (below 100 m) to the mountain region (3,050 m in Jumla), the highest point where rice is cultivated (14). However, the disease is particularly devastating in valleys, river basins, foothills, and hilly regions of Nepal (15). In susceptible varieties, the disease causes 10-20% yield reduction in Nepal, but in severe cases, it can go up to 80% (16). Farmers who lack resources are hesitant to utilize seed treatments containing systemic fungicides and foliar sprays with fungicides, despite the proven effectiveness of these methods in reducing the impact of blast disease (17). In addition, chemical usage is both impractical and harmful to the environment.

Continuous efforts have been made in Nepal to identify blast-resistant sources and develop resistant rice varieties (15). Despite the development of numerous resistant varieties against *Pyricularia oryzae*, the resistance they offer is not durable. This is due to the pathogen's high adaptability in different agricultural settings, causing the breakdown of single resistance genes within three to five years of the release of a particular cultivar (18). Also, varieties resistant to leaf blast may be susceptible to neck blast and vice versa. In addition, a genotype resistant in one location may be susceptible in another location. Therefore, this experiment was conducted to examine and screen different rice lines against neck blast and leaf blast and to elucidate if any kind of correlation exists between them. It was conducted in Gokarna, Lalitpur, one of the hot spots in Nepal where pathologists and breeders screen the germplasm for blast disease (15).

Research Methodology

Plant Materials

A rice blast disease screening nursery trial was conducted in Gokarna, Lalitpur in 2021 and 2022, consisting of 163 genotypes in 2021 and 181 genotypes in 2022, including two susceptible checks, Taichung-176 and Manjushree-2. These genotypes were selected from observation nursery trials, initial evaluation trials, coordinated varietal trials, farmers' field trials, high hill observation nursery trials and blast disease lines.

Experimental Design

Rice seeds were sown during the normal planting season for both years and transplanted when the seedlings were 25 days old. Each plot consisted of two rows, 1.5 meters in length, with a plant spacing of 20×15 cm, following an augmented design.

Cultural Practices

Fertilizer was applied as 120:30:30 NPK kg/ha as basal and (60:0:0 NPK kg/ha) as top dress. Two top dressings were applied: the first at 25 to 35 days after transplanting (30:0:0 NPK kg/ha) and the second at 50 to 60 days after transplanting (30:0:0 NPK kg/ha) or at the booting stage. Full-season irrigation was maintained until the grain maturity period to create a favorable environment for disease incidence.

Disease Scoring for Rice Blast and Statistical Data Analysis

Disease scoring was performed qualitatively at two stages: first at the tillering stage for leaf blast and secondly at the maturity stage for neck blast, following the rice standard evaluation system (SES) scale (IRRI, 2002). The lines were categorized into different categories of resistance and susceptibility based on the severity of the blast. Data was analyzed using MS Excel 2019 and S.

Table 1: Scale for scoring of leaf blast (1)

Scale	Disease Severity	Host Response
0	No lesions observed	Highly Resistant
1	Small brown specks of pin-point size or larger brown specks without sporulating center	Resistant
2	Small roundish to slightly elongated, necrotic gray spots, about 1-2 mm in diameter, with a distinct brown margin	Moderately Resistant
3	Lesion type is the same as in scale 2, but a significant number of lesions are on the upper leaves	Moderately Resistant
4	Typical susceptible blast lesions 3 mm or longer, infecting less than 4% of the leaf area	Moderately Susceptible
5	Typical blast lesions infecting 4-10% of the leaf area	Moderately Susceptible
6	6 Typical blast lesions infection 11-25% of the leaf area	Susceptible
7	7 Typical blast lesions infection 26-50% of the leaf area	Susceptible
8	Typical blast lesions infection 51-75% of the leaf area and many leaves are dead	Highly Susceptible
9	More than 75% leaf area affected	Highly Susceptible

Table 2: Scale for scoring of neck blast (1)

Scale	Disease severity	Host response
0	No visible lesions or observed lesions on only a few pedicels	Highly Resistant
1	Lesions on several pedicels or secondary branches	Resistant
3	Lesions on a few primary branches or the middle part of the panicle axis	Moderately Resistant
5	Lesion partially around the base (node) or the uppermost internode or the lower part of the panicle axis near the base	Moderately Susceptible
7	Lesion completely around panicle base or uppermost internode or panicle axis near base with more than 30% of filled grains	Susceptible
9	Lesion completely around panicle base or uppermost internode or the panicle axis near the base with less than 30% of filled grains.	Highly Susceptible

Results

Fig. 1: Rice genotypes showing different levels of resistance to neck blast during 2021 and 2022 at Gokarna- Lalitpur, Nepal

Fig. 2: Rice genotypes showing different levels of resistance to leaf blast during 2021 and 2022 at Gokarna- Lalitpur, Nepal

Table. 3: Rice genotypes showing highly resistant response to rice blast in the years 2021 and 2022

Experimental Year	Highly Resistant Genotypes
2021 (Neck Blast)	None of the genotypes show resistance.

2021 (Leaf Blast)	Purple rice, NR 11475-B-B-9-2, NR11341-B-B-32-1-2
2022 (Neck Blast)	NR 10676-B-5-3
2022 (Leaf Blast)	NR 11139-B-B-B-13-2, NR 11341-B-B-32-2, NR 11436-B-B-5, NR 11440-B-B-14, NR 11452-B-B-8, NR 11455-B-B-11-1, NR 11511-B-B-1, NR 11518-B-B-15, NR 11523-B-B-16, NR 11544-B-B-3, NR 11589-B-B-9, NR11303-B-B-20-3-1-2-2, NR 11443-B-B-10-1, NR 11200-B-42-3, NR 11303-B-B-5-3-2, NR 11340-B-B-42-3-1-1, NR 11345-B-B-2-3-2-1-3, NR 11374-B-B-17-2, NR 11377-B-B-22-1, NR 11381-B-B-17-2, NR 11382-B-B-5-2, NR 11455-B-B-1, NR 11467-B-B-9, NR 11468-B-B-13-2, NR 11515-B-B-1, NR 11519-B-B-14, NR 11554-B-B-1, NR 11568-B-B-5, NR 11476-B-B-10-1, NR 11572-B-B-11, NR 11572-B-B-6, NR 11586-B-B-12, NR 11592-B-B-6, NR11366-B-B-6-1-2, NR11590-B-B-4, PR29399-B-2-2-1, NR 11475-B-B-9-2, NR11341-B-B-32-1-2, NR 10676-B-5-3, NR 11607-B-B-11, Manjushree 2, NR 11321-B-B-7-2-2, NR11654-B-B-1, NR11656-B-B-10, NR11674-B-B-1, NR11646-B-B-3, NR11653-B-B-2, NR11657-B-B-13, NR11666-B-B-7, NR11680-B-B-13, NR11657-B-B-9, NR11668-B-B-2, NR11668-B-B-12, NR11670-B-B-6, NR11670-B-B-7, NR11694-B-B-4, NR11647-B-B-10, NR11647-B-B-13, NR11653-B-B-6, NR11661-B-B-11, NR11662-B-B-7, NR11666-B-B-3, NR11666-B-B-6, NR11674-B-B-18, NR11701-B-B-3, NR11652-B-B-11, NR11654-B-B-10, NR11657-B-B-2, NR11662-B-B-1, NR11667-B-B-2, NR11675-B-B-7, NR11688-B-B-3, NR11696-B-B-13, NR11701-B-B-10

Table. 4: Rice genotypes showing resistant response for rice blast in the years 2021 and 2022

Experimental Year	Resistant genotypes
2021 (Neck Blast)	NR 11130-B-B-B-19-3, NR 10676-B-5-3, NGRC 01795, NR 11137-B-B-B-10
2021 (Leaf Blast)	Black fine rice, Chandannath-3, NR 11139-B-B-B-13-2, NR 11341-B-B-32-2, NR 11345-B-B-30-3-1, NR 11436-B-B-5, NR 11440-B-B-14, NR 11440-B-B-14-2, NR 11452-B-B-8, NR 11379-B-B-22-3, NR 11511-B-B-1, NR 11518-B-B-15, NR 11544-B-B-3, NR 11589-B-B-9, NR 11320-B-B-6-3-2, NR 11321-B-B-7-3, NR 11443-B-B-7, NR 11121-B-B-17-5-7-1, NR 11242-B-B-13-2-2-1, NR 11346-B-B-15-1-2, NR 11515-B-B-8, NR 11570-B-B-5, NR 11374-B-B-17-2, NR 11450-B-B-12-2, NR 11475-B-B-9-3, NR 11554-B-B-1, NR 11476-B-B-10-1, NR 11572-B-B-6, NR11590-B-B-4, NR 11139-B-B-B-5-3-2, NR 11301-B-B-19-3-2, NR 11345-B-B-15-1-2, NR 11581-B-B-3, NR 11475-B-B-4, NR 11578-B-B-11, NR11340-B-B-32-1-2-1-3, Lekali dhan-1, NR 11374-B-B-23, NR 11414-B-B-1-2-1, NR 11516-B-B-3, NR 11530-B-B-3, NR 11594-B-B-1, NR 10676-B-5-3, NR 11137-B-B-B-10, NR 11321-B-B-7-2-2, NR 11554-B-B-18, NR 11569-B-B-9
2022 (Neck Blast)	Black fine rice, NR 11105-B-B-27, NR 11115-B-B-31-3, NR 11130-B-B-B-19-3, NR 11379-B-B-22-3, NR 11415-B-B-7-1, NR 11443-B-B-10-1, NR 11443-B-B-7, NR 11475-B-B-9-3, NR 11476-B-B-10-1, NR 11571-B-B-5, NR 11581-B-B-3, NR 11607-B-B-11, NR11645-B-B-8, NR11647-B-B-10, NR11647-B-B-13, NR11648-B-B-12, NR11649-B-B-9, NR11653-B-B-6, NR11658-B-B-2, NR11661-B-B-11, NR11662-B-B-7, NR11666-B-B-3, NR11666-B-B-6, NR11674-B-B-18, NR11683-B-B-13, NR11686-B-B-11, NR11701-B-B-3

2022 (Leaf Blast)	<p>IR13K190, NR 11105-B-B-27, NR 11115-B-B-31-3, NR 11271-B-B-6, NR 11301-B-B-15-4, NR 11379-B-B-22-3, NR11345-B-B-2-3-2, NR11382-B-B-5-3-3-1, NR 11320-B-B-6-3-2, NR 11321-B-B-7-3, NR 11443-B-B-7, Khumal-4, NR 11105-B-B-20-2-1, NR 11301-B-B-1, NR 11463-B-B-13, NR 11474-B-B-1-1, NR 11477-B-B-2-2, NR 11507-B-B-19, NR 11516-B-B-11, NR 11540-B-B-14, NR 11577-B-B-11, NR 11585-B-B-18, NR 11586-B-B-15, NR 11589-B-B-18, NR10838-B-B-4, NR11348-B-B-37-3-1, NR11366-B-B-6-1-2-3-1, NR11451-B-B-7-2-3, NR 11139-B-B-5-3-2, NR 11301-B-B-19-3-2, NR 11345-B-B-15-1-2, NR 11571-B-B-5, NR 11581-B-B-3, NR 11475-B-B-4, NR 11578-B-B-11, NR11340-B-B-32-1-2-1-3, NR 11386-B-B-24-3-3-2, NR 11515-B-B-20, NR11366-B-B-6-1-2-1-1, NR 11554-B-B-18, NR 11530-B-B-3, NR 11594-B-B-1, NR 10676-B-5-3, NR 11137-B-B-B-10, NR 11321-B-B-7-2-2, NR 11554-B-B-18, NR 11569-B-B-9, NR11613-B-B-9-1, NR11628-B-B-23-5, NR11649-B-B-9, NR11658-B-B-2, NR11683-B-B-13, NR11686-B-B-11, NR11650-B-B-9, NR11663-B-B-9, NR11667-B-B-7, NR11668-B-B-11, NR11686-B-B-4, NR11688-B-B-12, NR11696-B-B-11</p>

Table. 5: Rice genotypes showing moderately resistant response for rice blast in the years 2021 and 2022

Experimental Year	Moderately Resistant genotypes
2021 (Neck Blast)	<p>Black fine rice, Chandannath-3, IR13K190, NR 11105-B-B-27, NR 11115-B-B-31-3, NR 11139-B-B-13-2, NR 11271-B-B-6, NR 11301-B-B-15-4, NR 11341-B-B-32-2, NR 11345-B-B-30-3-1, NR 11436-B-B-5, NR 11440-B-B-14, NR 11440-B-B-14-2, NR 11452-B-B-8, NR 11455-B-B-11-1, NR 11379-B-B-22-3, NR 11511-B-B-1, NR 11518-B-B-15, NR 11523-B-B-16, NR 11544-B-B-3, NR 11589-B-B-9, NR11303-B-B-20-3-1-2-2, NR11345-B-B-2-3-2, NR11382-B-B-5-3-3-1, NR 11100-B-B-15-2-1, NR 11305-B-B-4-4-2, NR 11320-B-B-6-3-2, NR 11321-B-B-7-3, NR 11443-B-B-10-1, NR 11380-B-B-9-3-2, NR 11570-B-B-8, NR 682-B-B-3, NR11345-B-B-6-2-3, Khumal-8, Lekali dhan-3, NGRC 01786, NGRC 01787, NGRC 03161, NGRC 03162, NGRC 08598, NR 11121-B-B-17-5-7-1, NR 11139-B-B-6-2, NR 11242-B-B-13-2-2-1, NR 11346-B-B-15-1-2, NR 11447-B-B-3, NR 11475-B-B-6, NR 11476-B-B-1, NR 11515-B-B-8, NR 11570-B-B-5, NR10859-1-7-2-1, NR11341-B-B-30, NR11346-B-B-26-1-3, Purple rice, NR 11476-B-B-10-1, NR 11581-B-B-3, NR 11607-B-B-11</p>

<p>2021 (Leaf Blast)</p>	<p>IR13K190, NR 11105-B-B-27, NR 11115-B-B-31-3, NR 11271-B-B-6, NR 11301-B-B-15-4, NR 11130-B-B-B-19-3, NR 11455-B-B-11-1, NR 11523-B-B-16, NR 11415-B-B-7-1, NR11303-B-B-20-3-1-2-2, NR11345-B-B-2-3-2, NR11382-B-B-5-3-3-1, NR 11100-B-B-15-2-1, NR 11305-B-B-4-4-2, NR 11443-B-B-10-1, NR 11380-B-B-9-3-2, NR 11570-B-B-8, NR 682-B-B-B-3, NR11345-B-B-6-2-3, Lekali dhan-3, NGRC 03161, NGRC 08598, NR 11139-B-B-B-6-2, NR 11447-B-B-3, NR 11475-B-B-6, NR 11476-B-B-1, NR10859-1-7-2-1, NR11341-B-B-30, NR11346-B-B-26-1-3, Khumal-4, NR 11105-B-B-20-2-1, NR 11200-B-42-3, NR 11301-B-B-1, NR 11303-B-B-5-3-2, NR 11340-B-B-42-3-1-1, NR 11344-B-B-30-3-1-3, NR 11345-B-B-2-3-2-1-3, NR 11377-B-B-22-1, NR 11381-B-B-17-2, NR 11382-B-B-5-2, NR 11455-B-B-1, NR 11463-B-B-13, NR 11467-B-B-9, NR 11474-B-B-1-1, NR 11477-B-B-2-2, NR 11507-B-B-19, NR 11516-B-B-11, NR 11519-B-B-14, NR 11531-B-B-1, NR 11540-B-B-14, NR 11568-B-B-5, NR 11572-B-B-11, NR 11577-B-B-11, NR 11585-B-B-18, NR 11586-B-B-12, NR 11586-B-B-15, NR 11589-B-B-18, NR 11592-B-B-6, NR10838-B-B-4, NR11348-B-B-37-3-1, NR11366-B-B-6-1-2, NR11451-B-B-7-2-3, PR29399-B-2-2-1, NR 11121-B-B-17-5-3, NR 11366-B-B-26-3-3-2, NR 11378-B-B-5-2, NR 11571-B-B-5, NR 11447-B-B-10-1, NR 11572-B-B-20, NR11340-B-B-32-1-2-1-1, NR11345-B-B-6-2-2, NR11348-B-B-3-3-3, NR11348-B-B-37-3-3, NR11598-B-B-11-4, IR 88965-39-1-6-4, Khumal-10, Khumal-11, Khumal-13, NGRC 01782, NGRC 01783, NR 11323-B-B-1-1-2, NR 11453-B-B-13, NR 11515-B-B-6, NR 11516-B-B-1, NR 11516-B-B-5, NR10490, NR10676, NR 11607-B-B-11, Manjushree 2, NR 11366-B-B-26-3-2, NR 11386-B-B-24-3-3-2, NR 11515-B-B-20, NR11366-B-B-6-1-2-1-1, NR 11516-B-B-8, NR11366-B-B-26-2-3, Taichung 176, NR11474-B-B-10-2</p>
<p>2022 (Neck Blast)</p>	<p>Chandannath-3, NR 11271-B-B-6, NR 11455-B-B-11-1, NR 11523-B-B-16, NR 11544-B-B-3, NR 11100-B-B-15-2-1, NR 11320-B-B-6-3-2, NR 11301-B-B-1, NR 11381-B-B-17-2, NR 11540-B-B-14, NR 11554-B-B-1, NR 11589-B-B-18, NR11366-B-B-6-1-2, NR 11301-B-B-19-3-2, NR 11475-B-B-4, NR 11336-B-B-26-2-2-3, NR11646-B-B-3, NR11653-B-B-2, NR11657-B-B-13, NR11666-B-B-7, NR11680-B-B-13, NR11705-B-B-6</p>
<p>2022 (Leaf Blast)</p>	<p>Black fine rice, Chandannath-3, NR 11345-B-B-30-3-1, NR 11440-B-B-14-2, NR 11130-B-B-19-3, NR 11415-B-B-7-1, NR 11100-B-B-15-2-1, NR 11305-B-B-4-4-2, NR 11380-B-B-9-3-2, NR 11570-B-B-8, NR 682-B-B-B-3, NR11345-B-B-6-2-3, NR 11450-B-B-12-2, NR 11475-B-B-9-3, NR 11520-B-B-17, NR 11121-B-B-17-5-3, NR 11366-B-B-26-3-3-2, NR 11378-B-B-5-2, NR 11447-B-B-10-1, NR 11572-B-B-20, NR11340-B-B-32-1-2-1-1, NR11345-B-B-6-2-2, NR11348-B-B-3-3-3, NR11348-B-B-37-3-3, NR11598-B-B-11-4, NR 11336-B-B-26-2-2-3, NR 11516-B-B-8, NR11366-B-B-26-2-3, Taichung 176, NR11663-B-B-15, NR11645-B-B-8, NR11648-B-B-12, NR11649-B-B-10, NR11656-B-B-3, NR11663-B-B-13, NR11671-B-B-8, NR11678-B-B-7, NR11621-B-B-5-2, US 312</p>

Table. 6: Rice genotypes showing moderately susceptible response for rice blast in the years 2021 and 2022

Experimental Year	Moderately Susceptible genotypes
2021 (Neck Blast)	NR 11415-B-B-7-1, NR 11443-B-B-7, Khumal-4, NR 11105-B-B-20-2-1, NR 11200-B-42-3, NR 11301-B-B-1, NR 11303-B-B-5-3-2, NR 11340-B-B-42-3-1-1, NR 11344-B-B-30-3-1-3, NR 11345-B-B-2-3-2-1-3, NR 11374-B-B-17-2, NR 11377-B-B-22-1, NR 11381-B-B-17-2, NR 11382-B-B-5-2, NR 11450-B-B-12-2, NR 11455-B-B-1, NR 11463-B-B-13, NR 11467-B-B-9, NR 11468-B-B-13-2, NR 11474-B-B-1-1, NR 11475-B-B-9-3, NR 11477-B-B-2-2, NR 11507-B-B-19, NR 11515-B-B-1, NR 11516-B-B-11, NR 11519-B-B-14, NR 11520-B-B-17, NR 11531-B-B-1, NR 11540-B-B-14, NR 11554-B-B-1, NR 11568-B-B-5, NR 11572-B-B-11, NR 11572-B-B-6, NR 11577-B-B-11, NR 11585-B-B-18, NR 11586-B-B-12, NR 11586-B-B-15, NR 11589-B-B-18, NR 11592-B-B-6, NR10838-B-B-4, NR11348-B-B-37-3-1, NR11366-B-B-6-1-2, NR11366-B-B-6-1-2-3-1, NR11451-B-B-7-2-3, NR11590-B-B-4, PR29399-B-2-2-1, NR 11121-B-B-17-5-3, NR 11139-B-B-5-3-2, NR 11301-B-B-19-3-2, NR 11345-B-B-15-1-2, NR 11366-B-B-26-3-3-2, NR 11378-B-B-5-2, NR 11571-B-B-5, NR 11447-B-B-10-1, NR 11475-B-B-4, NR 11475-B-B-9-2, NR 11572-B-B-20, NR 11578-B-B-11, NR11340-B-B-32-1-2-1-1, NR11340-B-B-32-1-2-1-3, NR11341-B-B-32-1-2, NR11345-B-B-6-2-2, NR11348-B-B-3-3-3, NR11348-B-B-37-3-3, NR11598-B-B-11-4, Chandannath-1, IR 88965-39-1-6-4, Khumal-10, Khumal-11, Khumal-13, Lekali dhan-1, NGRC 01781, NGRC 01782, NGRC 01783, NGRC 01796, NGRC 03160, NR 11323-B-B-1-1-2, NR 11374-B-B-23, NR 11414-B-B-1-2-1, NR 11453-B-B-13, NR 11515-B-B-6, NR 11516-B-B-1, NR 11516-B-B-3, NR 11516-B-B-5, NR 11530-B-B-3, NR 11594-B-B-1, NR10490, NR10676
2021 (Leaf Blast)	Khumal-8, NGRC 01786, NGRC 01787, NGRC 03162, NR 11468-B-B-13-2, NR 11515-B-B-1, NR 11520-B-B-17, NR11366-B-B-6-1-2-3-1, Chandannath-1, NGRC 01781, NGRC 03160, NGRC 01795, NR 11336-B-B-26-2-2-3
2022 (Neck Blast)	NR 11139-B-B-13-2, NR 11301-B-B-15-4, NR 11341-B-B-32-2, NR 11452-B-B-8, NR 11589-B-B-9, NR11345-B-B-2-3-2, NR 11382-B-B-5-2, NR 11463-B-B-13, NR 11468-B-B-13-2, NR 11477-B-B-2-2, NR 11568-B-B-5, PR29399-B-2-2-1, NR11348-B-B-37-3-3, NR 11321-B-B-7-2-2, NR 11386-B-B-24-3-3-2, NR11366-B-B-6-1-2-1-1, NR 11516-B-B-8, NR11649-B-B-12, NR11657-B-B-9, NR11665-B-B-11, NR11668-B-B-2, NR11668-B-B-12, NR11670-B-B-6, NR11670-B-B-7, NR11694-B-B-4, NR11702-B-B-14, NR11613-B-B-9-1, NR11628-B-B-23-5
2022 (Leaf Blast)	NR 11344-B-B-30-3-1-3, NR 11531-B-B-1, NR 11366-B-B-26-3-2, NR11630-B-B-1-1, NR11688-B-B-7

Table. 7: Rice genotypes showing susceptible response for rice blast in the years 2021 and 2022

Experimental Year	Susceptible genotypes
2021 (Neck Blast)	Manjushree 2, NR 11321-B-B-7-2-2, NR 11336-B-B-26-2-2-3, NR 11366-B-B-26-3-2, NR 11386-B-B-24-3-3-2, NR 11515-B-B-20, NR11366-B-B-6-1-2-1-1, NR 11516-B-B-8, NR 11554-B-B-18, NR11366-B-B-26-2-3, Taichung 176, NGRC 01780, NGRC 01804, NR 11569-B-B-9, NR11474-B-B-10-2

2021 (Leaf Blast)	NGRC 01796, NGRC 01804
2022 (Neck Blast)	IR13K190, NR 11436-B-B-5, NR 11440-B-B-14, NR 11440-B-B-14-2, NR 11518-B-B-15, NR11303-B-B-20-3-1-2-2, NR11382-B-B-5-3-3-1, NR 11305-B-B-4-4-2, NR 11380-B-B-9-3-2, NR 11570-B-B-8, NR 682-B-B-B-3, NR11345-B-B-6-2-3, Khumal-4, NR 11105-B-B-20-2-1, NR 11303-B-B-5-3-2, NR 11340-B-B-42-3-1-1, NR 11345-B-B-2-3-2-1-3, NR 11450-B-B-12-2, NR 11455-B-B-1, NR 11467-B-B-9, NR 11474-B-B-1-1, NR 11507-B-B-19, NR 11520-B-B-17, NR 11572-B-B-11, NR 11577-B-B-11, NR 11585-B-B-18, NR 11586-B-B-15, NR 11592-B-B-6, NR10838-B-B-4, NR11366-B-B-6-1-2-3-1, NR11451-B-B-7-2-3, NR 11139-B-B-B-5-3-2, NR 11366-B-B-26-3-3-2, NR 11447-B-B-10-1, NR 11475-B-B-9-2, NR 11572-B-B-20, NR 11578-B-B-11, NR11341-B-B-32-1-2, NR11598-B-B-11-4, NR 11554-B-B-18
2022 (Leaf Blast)	-

Table. 8: Rice genotypes showing highly susceptible response for rice blast in the years 2021 and 2022

Experimental Year	Highly Susceptible genotypes
2021 (Neck Blast)	-
2021 (Leaf Blast)	NGRC 01780
2022 (Neck Blast)	NR 11345-B-B-30-3-1, NR 11511-B-B-1, NR 11321-B-B-7-3, NR 11200-B-42-3, NR 11344-B-B-30-3-1-3, NR 11374-B-B-17-2, NR 11377-B-B-22-1, NR 11515-B-B-1, NR 11516-B-B-11, NR 11519-B-B-14, NR 11531-B-B-1, NR 11572-B-B-6, NR 11586-B-B-12, NR11348-B-B-37-3-1, NR11590-B-B-4, NR 11121-B-B-17-5-3, NR 11345-B-B-15-1-2, NR 11378-B-B-5-2, NR11340-B-B-32-1-2-1-1, NR11340-B-B-32-1-2-1-3, NR11345-B-B-6-2-2, NR11348-B-B-3-3-3, Manjushree 2, NR 11366-B-B-26-3-2, NR 11515-B-B-20, NR11366-B-B-26-2-3, Taichung 176, NR11650-B-B-8, NR11654-B-B-1, NR11656-B-B-10, NR11663-B-B-15, NR11672-B-B-2, NR11674-B-B-1, NR11678-B-B-12, NR11630-B-B-1-1
2022 (Leaf Blast)	-

Discussion

Due to the availability of limited resources regarding blast disease management in Nepal and reluctance of farmers to use the chemicals before the incidence of the disease, the use of resistant cultivars is a crucial alternative on which farmers can rely. A total of 163 genotypes were scored in 2021 and 181 genotypes were screened in 2022. Among them, 114 genotypes were tested in both years, while 49 and 64 genotypes were new to the years 2021 and 2022 respectively. Altogether, 227 genotypes were screened for blast resistance in two years. Out of 114 recurring genotypes, only 16 genotypes for Neck blast and 35 for Leaf blast showed the same resistant level in both years (**Fig.1 and Fig.2**). This may be due to the dynamics of interaction between the environment and the pathotypes in natural epiphytotic conditions (20). In addition, under field conditions, it is reported that resistance in cultivars is decreased simultaneously after the cultivar is released for mass cultivations which might be due to the significant interaction between resistant varieties and locations (15).

Only NR 10676-B-5-3 was the genotype to show a highly resistant level for neck blast in any of the two years (**Table 3**). It showed a highly resistant response in 2022 for both neck blast along with leaf blast (**Table 3**) whereas resistant

response for both NB and LB in 2021 (**Table 4**). Similarly, NR 11130-B-B-19-3 was resistant to neck blast (**Table 4**) and moderately resistant to leaf blast in both years (**Table 5**). NR 11379-B-B-22-3 and NR 11581-B-B-3 were resistant to leaf blasts in both years while both of them were resistant to neck blasts in 2022 (**Table 4**) and moderately resistant in 2021 (**Table 5**). NR 11475-B-B-9-2 and NR11341-B-B-32-1-2 were highly resistant to leaf blasts across two years (**Table 3**) but showed moderately susceptible (**Table 6**) and susceptible reactions (**Table 7**) in 2021 and 2022 respectively. These were the notable genotypes from the experiment that can be good genetic resources for blast resistance breeding. However, they still require screening at multiple locations and further assessment at the genetic level to better understand their nature of resistance and real genetic value. While 18 genotypes showed highly resistant in 2022 and at least resistant in 2021 for leaf blast, only 2 of them were moderately resistant or better against neck blast in consecutive years. Hence, they can still be good resources for blast resistance but solely against leaf blast.

There were some promising genotypes but assessed only for the second year. NR11647-B-B-10, NR11647-B-B-13, NR11653-B-B-6, NR11661-B-B-11, NR11662-B-B-7, NR11666-B-B-3, NR11666-B-B-6, NR11674-B-B-18 and NR11701-B-B-3 showed resistance for neck blast (**Table 4**) and high resistance for leaf blast (**Table 3**) but were assessed only in 2022. Hence, these genotypes require further attention and assessment from pathologists and breeders.

Conclusion

Rice blast caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cavara is the most destructive disease of rice in Nepal. Altogether, 227 genotypes were screened for blast resistance in the years 2021 and 2022. Out of 114 recurring genotypes, only 16 genotypes for NB and 35 for LB showed the same resistant level in both years. This may be due to the dynamics of interaction between the environment and the pathotypes in natural epiphytotic conditions. These resistant and moderately resistant genotypes with desirable agronomical characteristics can be used as donor parents in resistance breeding programs for the development of leaf blast-resistant varieties. Also, in order to increase the resistance level in cultivars against blast disease, stacking of the multiple resistance genes could be performed during resistance breeding programs.

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